

Workshop Report

WP2 – European Universities Collaborative workshop 10 - 11 OCTOBER 2022

RitrainPlus

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Project Coordinator University Milano Bicocca

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SUMMARY

On the 10th and 11th of October 2022, the Collaborative Workshop hosted by the WP2 of the RiTrain Plus project was held at UNIBO, in Bologna.

The workshop was an important occasion of networking and allowed a constructive discussion between representatives of various institutions involved in the **Ritrain Plus** Project, the **UNA.Europa** alliance and the respective project related to Research Infrastructures, **UNA.Resin**.

Representatives of both projects presented the results achieved in the tasks so far completed. The research conducted confirmed the urgent need for a training programme to prepare future managers of research centres and enable the continuing training of those who are already holding such positions in the field.

In order to accomplish this objective, collaboration between universities, research centres and every other possible stakeholder involved is essential, given the inter-connection between them.

Accordingly, to the objectives of RiTrain Plus WP2 - It is been highlighted the urge to the introduction of theoretical and practical teachings for managerial skills, throughout the entire university career (Bachelor, Master and PhD), and moreover, the need for the universities' governance to understand the importance of these courses in order to undertake their inclusion in the training programmes of their institutions.

During the workshop, a group work was carried out to identify, the presence in universities of courses on the topics identified as strategic by Task 2.1.

It emerged that although there are existing courses with compatible learning outcomes, there is a lack of offer and an urge for a much-structured approach.

It was therefore discussed the possible ways to integrate the existing courses and to insert new ones by assuming the realization of a training path, possibly widespread, with the opportunity for students to acquire credits in different institutions through distance learning or mobility programs.

This purpose, as already suggested in RiTrain Plus proposal, could be fulfilled through the use of micro-credentials. Nevertheless, this flexible tool, in order to gain efficiency, will require a wide support from the highest number of university and institutions in addition to a clear regulation and accreditation process.

This proposal was widely appreciated by the representatives of UNA.Europa who requested its presentation to the Board of Directors in mid-November.

In addition to the importance of training a new generation of managers, the workshop discussed the activity of mapping research infrastructures across Europe.

It was reiterated the need to create a strong network between existing infrastructures that will allow the realization of the open science and open research area, pursuing the objectives of efficiency and sustainability.

Exchanges of best practices between countries should also be further implemented, encouraging and ensuring mobility of students and professionals.

Accordingly, the activities carried out during the implementation of the UNA.Resin project were analysed and possible pathways for the future have been discussed.

The event was highly appreciated by the participants and the new ideas and connections made will serve a powerful resource for future collaboration and for advancing in the objectives of both projects.

The agenda can be seen below, and has been completed with speaker summaries, highlighting key takeaways.

Agenda

Day 1 - Oct 10th 2022	
13:00-14:00	Arrival & Lunch
<i>The two projects: Results presentation</i>	
14:00-14:30	The RITrainPlus vision <i>Speaker: Antonino Rotolo (University of Bologna)</i>
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - There is a strong need for collaboration between RIs and Universities. They are autonomous entities that have to cooperate for a common goal - Exchange of personnel, resources and instruments is the goal - It is important that career paths and professional roles needed inside the RIs and CFs are made known since the bachelor level - Elimination of bias in communication regarding the research field is a priority - Una.Europa can have a great impact creating a commitment within universities in introducing LAs embedded in existing courses and promoting a LLT on managerial skills. - Strategic new alliances between RITrain Plus project and the future follow up to UNA.Resin project can be made
14:30-15:00	The Una.Resin vision <i>Speaker: Seth Amanfo (University of Edinburgh)</i>
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Objective of the Project Una.Resin is the creation of a common R&I eco-system <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • sharing of research strengths, infrastructure and resources • developing a vision of common research culture

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • involving citizens and non-academic actors across all regions of our eco-system (Open research) • collaborating with other European University Alliances, sharing experiences and learning from each other <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The six clusters of the project were illustrated (Research Coordination, Research Infrastructure, Research Career and Culture, Open Research, Citizen Engagement, Public Private and Third Sector) - New fundings for the future need to be guaranteed – UnaFutura is a possibility
15:00-15:20	<p>RITrainPlus D2.1 results Identifying and Updating Training needs in European Research Infrastructures and Core Facilities</p> <p><i>Speaker: Dimitri Pradner (Johannes Kepler University of Linz)</i></p>
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The important results of Task 2.1 were presented to the participants to the workshop highlighting the training needs of European Research Infrastructures - The methodology of the study was illustrated to the participants outside RiTrain team <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • combining a quantitative online-survey among 330 members of RIs and CFs with 17 qualitative guided interviews among managers from eight structurally selected countries • the motivation and doxa of RI and CFs managers from different fields were analyzed - Seven skills were identified as necessary: <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. communication and engagement 2. leadership and staff management 3. positioning in the scientific community 4. academic excellence & broad and deep academic understanding for the field 5. project management & organisation management 6. deeper knowledge about the field of science and research in Europe 7. communication skills on different levels
15:20-15:40	<p>Una.Resin D2.1 results Research Infrastructures and Resources: Mapping, Strategy and Pilot Actions</p> <p><i>Speaker: Veerle Bruggeman (KU Leuven), Alessia Franchini and Emilio Urbinati (University of Bologna)</i></p>
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Speaker have illustrated the WPs of UNA.Resin towards a common R&I eco-system with a special focus on WP2 (Sharing Research Infrastructures and Resources (RIRs)) - The methodology followed three important steps: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Mapping of Research Infrastructures and Resources • Shared Strategy and Action Plan for sharing RIR (co-creation WS) • Co-deign of pilot actions to share and open RIR - Necessity for the engagement of a wide community of stakeholders in order to create a common space of knowledge, tools and practices exchange - Illustration of the main barriers to sharing of RIRs accordingly to the area

<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Presentation of the results of the co-creation workshop, including the solution founded to the main barriers - Next pilot actions will be: the creation of a blueprint of a RIRs catalogue and the creation of a network of experts promoting research collaboration <p><i>ENGAGEMENT AND UPSKILLING OF THE UNA EUROPA COMMUNITY OF ACADEMICS AND PROFESSIONALS IS KEY</i></p>	
15:40-16:00	Coffee Break
<i>Co-creation of the Learning Activities</i>	
16:00-17:45	<p>Group work on IRs and CF world</p> <p><i>Facilitators: Monica Forni, Antonino Rotolo, Emilio Urbinati, Alessia Franchini</i></p>
<p>The group work focused on the six LAs that were addressed by the WP2 of RiTrain Plus as essential to train future managers of RIs. The participants were asked to evaluate if the activities were in any form present in their universities, which were or should be the Learning Outcomes of each LA and the number of ECTS needed to fulfil them.</p> <p>Various answers were given but what emerged was:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • a general lack of the needed activities, • the presence of some courses eligible to include the addressed LAs and • the urge to a deeper investigation within the represented universities <p>It was agreed by the participants:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • maintain the courses in a mixed mode (virtual and in presence) • offer them in English (in order for students to get used to the international environment since the BA level) • everyone should explore their institution's readiness to host new courses centred on the pre-designed LAs 	
17:45-18:00	<p>Wrap-up of the day</p> <p><i>Speaker: Monica Forni (UNIBO)</i></p>
<p>It was requested to the audience to keep up the good collaboration and research within their own Institutions, trying to introduce to the proper organs the idea of the introductions of the aforementioned courses. The collaboration from all levels of the University and Research Infrastructure hierarchy is vital to the outcome of the Project and the reach of the pre-determined goals.</p>	
20:30	Workshop Dinner – Ristorante <i>“La Scalinatella”</i> - Via Caduti di Cefalonia, 5/e, 40125 Bologna BO

Day 2 - Oct 11th 2022	
<i>Universities engagement</i>	
9:00 – 9:30	<p>A strategic vision for coordinated training actions and for a European School for Management of Research Infrastructures (ESMRI)</p> <p><i>Speaker: Marialuisa Lavitrano (University of Milano Bicocca - Project Leader RiTrain Plus – Director of EMMRI Master)</i></p>
<p>Prof. Lavitrano highlighted the widely recognised urgency to create an integrated a path to educate the Research Infrastructures’ managers of the future.</p> <p>UNIMIB has, through the first edition of the European project RiTrain, developed an executive master in management of research (EMMRI - https://emmri.unimib.it/) which has proved itself very useful for professionals of the field.</p> <p>Through the experience gained from the EMMRI master and the many years of field experience of many of the participants, RitrainPlus will be able to offer a better and more comprehensive training experience.</p>	
9:30 - 9:50	<p>Research Infrastructure and Core Facilities in Finland</p> <p><i>Speaker: Marko Peura (University of Helsinki)</i></p>
<p>Presentation of the Research Infrastructure development plans of University of Helsinki trough it’s participation to the ESFRI roadmap and its strategic role in Finland.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • A complete map of the financing plan of the RIs, followed by an insight on investments on life cycle planning in order to promote a sustainable development of RIs. • Establishment of the economic sustainability of the Infrastructures based on the adoption of an open but not free of charge access. • RIs are also places in which users can apprehend practices related to open science following the guide principle “as open as possible as closed as necessary”. 	
9:50 – 10:20	<p>Digital micro-credential system</p> <p><i>Speaker: Paolo Cherubini (University of Pavia)</i></p>
<p>The speaker, Prof. Paolo Cherubini, unfortunately couldn’t attend the workshop but the subject of micro-credentials, as a useful tool to create a wide recognition of the LAs between different Universities, has been commonly addressed as a solution to the fragmentation between different institutions.</p>	

A deeper conversation within the BoD of Una.Europa that will be held in mid-November has been proposed from the representatives of the alliance, asking for the presence of a representant of RITrainPlus to clearly explain the needs and the goals of the project.

10:20- 10:40	<p>The role of Universitie’s alliance and associations in the mutual recognition of ECTS</p> <p><i>Speaker: Kristof Vlaeminck (Una Europa)</i></p>
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The speaker has presented the goals of UNA.Europa alliance and the objectives for the future

- designing the university of the future
- attracting external fundings for the association
- have an impact on universities’ education, research and service to society

The collaboration between the partner universities in different fields are designing Joint European degrees, joint doctoral programmes and Micro-Credentials as a tool for flexible learning pathways.

The plan of the Alliance will be the creation of an Inter-University Campus creating opportunities of virtual mobility and community building.

Through the sequence of projects (1Europe and UNA.Resin) the pathway for a UNA.Europa’s roll-out project has been prepared with the aim of involving a broader group of participants, strengthening the core values of European universities and developing the most innovative educational programmes.

10:40 -11:00	Coffee Break
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11:00 -12:00	<p>List of future actions and wrap-up of the day</p> <p><i>Speaker: Antonino Rotolo</i></p>
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CONCLUSIONS:

- It is required that the participants to the workshop disseminate inside their institutions the informations acquired during these days
- A proposal on micro-credentials and LAs (with their LOs) must be defined an presented to the BoD of UNA.Europa in order to promote the RITrain Task 2.2 goals inside the alliance
- The objective of WP5 – the creation of the European School for Managers of Research Infrastructures (ESMRI), created on the model of the European University Institute (EUI), will further be discussed in the Workshop of May
- The school will have the duty of both delivery the courses, collect the activities from other Universitites and accreditate the courses.

Speaker list (alphabetical order)

We thank all the workshop contributors for their contributions to the workshop as well as this summary document.

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